

Certified Educators' Perceptions of Math Response to Instruction and Intervention Implementation in Rural Tennessee Middle Schools: A Qualitative Study

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Abstract

Response to Instruction and Intervention (RTI²) implementation presents unique challenges in rural middle schools, particularly in mathematics instruction. While extensively studied at the elementary level and in reading instruction, limited research exists on math RTI² implementation at the middle school level, especially in rural settings. This qualitative interpretive study examined certified educators' perceptions of math RTI² implementation in rural Tennessee middle schools. Data was collected via a questionnaire from 25 certified educators across nine rural Tennessee districts who provided math instruction during designated intervention time. Through systematic coding and analysis, three primary benefits emerged: improved academic performance on state assessments, increased student confidence and skill mastery, and advantages of small-group instruction. Key barriers included non-math certified teachers leading intervention groups, time and resource constraints, and student engagement challenges. Results indicate a critical need for enhanced professional development and support systems, particularly for non-math-certified educators tasked with providing math intervention. These findings contribute to the limited literature on rural middle school math intervention and provide insights for improving RTI² implementation in similar settings.

Keywords: response to intervention, mathematics instruction, rural education, middle school education, teacher perceptions

Background

The implementation of Response to Instruction and Intervention (RTI²) emerged from the 2004 reauthorization of the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA), which permitted its use as an alternative to the IQ-Achievement discrepancy model for identifying students with specific learning disabilities (IDEA, 2004). Educational leaders also chose RTI² because it met the federally mandated guidelines of No Child Left Behind (2002), which required schools to use evidence-based teaching practices for all students (Fuchs, D. & Fuchs, L. S., 2017; Sanger et al., 2012).

Tennessee's approach to RTI² evolved beyond the traditional three-tiered model focused solely on special education eligibility. In 2014, state leaders restructured the framework to emphasize instructional opportunities for all students (Berkeley et al., 2020). This shift aimed to create a comprehensive system supporting academic growth while maintaining the capability to identify students with specific learning disabilities.

Statement of the Problem

While researchers have extensively examined reading interventions and RTI² at the elementary level, limited information exists on math RTI², particularly in middle schools (Bouck & Cosby, 2018; Ciullo et al., 2016). Fuchs et al. (2007) recognized this narrow focus on math instruction and intervention research, a trend that has continued. The implementation of RTI² in Grades 6-8 presents unique challenges, including questions about:

- appropriate instructional personnel selection
- optimal intervention duration
- scheduling logistics
- assessment methods for tier placement

- support for non-tiered students during intervention time

Significance of the Study

This research addresses a significant gap in the literature regarding math RTI² implementation in rural middle schools. While RTI² is intended for all educational settings, most research has focused on medium and large school districts (Bailey, 2014). Furthermore, the prevalence of non-math certified teachers providing math intervention highlights the need to understand educator perceptions and experiences in this context.

Research Questions

This study addressed two primary research questions:

- RQ1: What were the perceptions of certified educators who taught math intervention or instruction during core extension time about the benefits, if any, of math Response to Instruction and Intervention (RTI²) in rural Tennessee middle school districts?
- RQ2: What were the perceptions of certified educators who taught math intervention or instruction during core extension time about the barriers, if any, of math Response to Instruction and Intervention (RTI²) in rural Tennessee middle school districts?

Literature Review

Educational leaders chose RTI as an alternative framework method to the IQ Achievement Discrepancy Model after the 2004 reauthorization of the IDEA (IDEA, 2004). Leaders chose RTI because it met the

federally mandated guidelines of NCLB (2002), which stated schools should use evidence-based teaching practices for all students (Deno et al., 2009; Fuchs, D. & Fuchs, L. S., 2017; NCLB, 2002; Sanger et al., 2012; Swanson et al., 2012). Educators implemented the multitiered prevention system of RTI as it “integrates increasingly intensive instruction and, at each layer, employs assessment to identify students who are inadequately responsive and who therefore require intervention at the next, more intensive layer in the system” (Fuchs, L. S. & Fuchs, D., 2006, p. 621). Ideally, RTI could be utilized as a framework to prevent long-term academic failure and not solely be used for identifying and serving students with disabilities (Fuchs, L. S. & Fuchs, D., 2006). Researchers defined RTI as a prevention model of multitiered instruction (Bouck & Cosby, 2018; Bouck et al., 2019; Dennis, 2015; Dobbins et al., 2014; Donovan & Shepherd, 2013; Fuchs et al., 2007). The Tennessee Department of Education (TDOE) developed its own framework called Response to Instruction and Intervention (RTI²).

Bailey (2014) found no consistent approach to RTI² implementation even though many schools received the same training for RTI². Researchers noted the implementation of RTI² in Grades 6-8 was met with questions and concerns from educators such as who should teach the interventions, duration of interventions, how to schedule time for interventions, and the most reliable form of assessment to determine tier placement for students (Bouck & Cosby, 2018; Bouck et al., 2019; Ciullo et al., 2016; Faggella-Luby & Wardwell, 2011; Fuchs et al., 2010; Prewett et al., 2012). Although researchers reported all educators had a role in the delivery of high-fidelity instruction during RTI² implementation, teachers found the hiring of

non-qualified personnel as RTI² coaches and core extension instructors as a major concern in the implementation process (King, 2011; TDOE, 2013). Robinson et al. (2013) noted rural school districts faced problems recruiting and retaining highly effective teachers and providing evidence-based instruction due to a lack of funding.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative interpretive methodology to examine educators' perceptions of math RTI² implementation. This approach was particularly appropriate for understanding educators' perspectives on RTI² implementation, as it allowed for rich, detailed responses about their experiences and challenges with implementing math intervention in rural middle schools.

Participants and Setting

The study utilized purposeful sampling followed by snowball sampling to identify qualified participants across rural Tennessee school districts. Initial participants were selected based on three primary criteria: current certification as educators in rural Tennessee districts, active involvement in delivering math instruction during RTI² intervention time, and current teaching assignments in Grades 6-8. This sampling approach yielded 25 certified educators from nine rural Tennessee school districts.

The participant pool represented a diverse range of teaching certifications and assignments. Of the 25 participants, twelve (48%) held math certification, while thirteen (52%) were certified in other subject areas, including science, English language arts, physical education, history, and special education. This distribution reflected the reality in many rural schools where non-math-certified teachers are often called upon

to provide math intervention. Regarding RTI² teaching assignments, seventeen participants (68%) worked with non-tiered groups, six (24%) taught Tier II groups, and two (8%) led Tier III groups.

Data Collection

Data collection proceeded through a carefully designed multi-step process. The primary instrument was a questionnaire developed through extensive review of existing literature on RTI² implementation and refined through expert feedback and pilot testing. Five educators participated in the pilot study, providing valuable feedback that led to the clarification of questions and the addition of key definitions, particularly regarding non-tiered students.

The final questionnaire comprised five open-ended questions designed to elicit detailed responses about implementation experiences, two multiple-select questions addressing specific aspects of RTI² practice, and a demographics section. The instrument also included space for additional comments, allowing participants to share insights beyond the structured questions. The questions were as follows:

1. Do you currently deliver math instruction during core extension at the middle school level?
2. What tier do you primarily provide instruction for? Choose one:
 - A. Non-tiered students (i.e., students who do not receive Tier II or Tier III services but still receive math instruction during core extension)
 - B. Tier II
 - C. Tier III
3. What does math core extension look like in your school? (Examples: Who provides the instruction? Do all

students participate in core extension?)

4. What benefits for teachers or students, if any, have you seen since math core extension was implemented in your school?
5. What barriers for teachers or students, if any, have you seen since math core extension was implemented in your school?

The data collection process began after securing IRB approval. Initial contact was made with ten purposefully selected educators who met the study criteria. Through snowball sampling, these participants recommended additional qualified educators, expanding the participant pool. Participants received the questionnaire through a secure online platform and were given a two-week response window. Data collection continued until reaching saturation point, where new responses no longer yielded novel insights.

Data Analysis

Analysis followed a systematic three-stage coding process designed to identify and refine themes within the data. The first stage involved open coding, where initial review of all responses led to identification of recurring concepts and development of preliminary categories. During this phase, particular attention was paid to specific examples and experiences shared by participants regarding both benefits and challenges of RTI² implementation.

The second stage employed axial coding, where related concepts were grouped into broader categories. This process revealed connections between various aspects of RTI² implementation, such as the relationship between teacher qualification and perceived implementation effectiveness. The final stage, selective

coding, integrated these categories into core themes directly addressing the research questions.

Results

Analysis of participant responses revealed distinct patterns regarding both the benefits and challenges of math RTI² implementation in rural middle schools. The findings aligned clearly with the study's two primary research questions, illuminating both successes and obstacles in current implementation practices.

Research Question 1: Perceived Benefits

The analysis revealed three primary categories of benefits associated with math RTI² implementation. The first significant benefit, reported by 28% of participants, centered on improved academic performance. Educators consistently noted increases in end-of-year assessment scores, with several specifically mentioning recovery to pre-COVID achievement levels. As one teacher explained, "Our scores have increased back to what they were prior to COVID-19" (Participant 11). This academic improvement manifested not only in standardized test scores but also in classroom-based assessments and daily mathematical performance.

The second and most frequently cited benefit, mentioned by 36% of participants, involved student growth and confidence. Teachers observed significant improvements in students' mathematical self-efficacy and willingness to engage with challenging material. One particularly illustrative response came from Participant 15, who noted, "Math core has benefited many students as far as building up of basic skills that they need in order to feel successful in the Tier I classroom. These students feel more confident when they successfully master a skill." This growth in confidence appeared to correlate with improved classroom participation and

willingness to attempt more challenging mathematical tasks.

The third benefit category, cited by 24% of participants, focused on instructional advantages, particularly those associated with small-group instruction and individualized attention. Teachers reported that the RTI² framework allowed them to provide more targeted instruction and respond more effectively to individual student needs. As Participant 2 explained, "The ability for every single student to receive some sort of small group tiered instruction is something that I, in turn, see the benefits of in my own math classroom." This structure enabled teachers to identify and address specific skill gaps while providing appropriate challenges for students at all achievement levels.

Research Question 2: Perceived Barriers

The study also revealed several significant challenges in implementing math RTI² effectively in rural middle schools. The most prominent barrier, identified by 40% of participants, concerned staffing and qualification issues. The practice of assigning non-math-certified teachers to lead intervention groups emerged as a particular concern. Participant 17 articulated this challenge clearly: "Not all teachers are good at math so being able to help students could be a problem. I have heard other teachers complain about not understanding math enough to help." This situation appeared particularly problematic in rural schools where staffing options were often limited.

Time and resource constraints emerged as the second major barrier, mentioned by 20% of participants. Teachers expressed concern about balancing intervention time with core instruction requirements. The increased planning demands associated with intervention groups created additional strain on already busy schedules. One teacher's response captured this tension: "The time required each day

for RTI² is time taken away from class instruction" (Participant 14). This challenge was exacerbated by limited planning time and resources typical in rural school settings.

Student engagement issues constituted the third significant barrier, cited by 24% of participants. Teachers reported difficulties maintaining student motivation and participation, particularly among Tier II students. As Participant 23 observed, "A large percentage of students in Tier II are there based on lack of effort, not a learning barrier. The pattern is clearly seen by grades 7 and 8." This observation suggests a need for strategies specifically designed to engage middle school students in intervention activities.

Discussion

The findings from this study provide significant insights into the implementation of math RTI² in rural middle schools, revealing both encouraging successes and persistent challenges that warrant careful consideration.

The reported improvements in academic performance align with previous research by Dulaney (2012), suggesting that RTI² can effectively support struggling students when implemented with fidelity. However, these findings extend beyond previous work by highlighting the particular importance of student confidence and engagement in middle school mathematics. The emphasis participants placed on increased student confidence represents a particularly noteworthy finding, as it suggests that well-implemented RTI² programs can address both academic and affective aspects of mathematical learning.

The prevalence of non-math certified teachers leading intervention groups emerges as a critical challenge requiring immediate attention. While previous research by King (2011) identified staffing

challenges in rural schools, these findings suggest this issue may be more acute in middle school mathematics, where content expertise becomes increasingly crucial. The situation raises important questions about the preparation and support needed for non-math-certified teachers tasked with mathematical intervention.

The time and resource constraints identified by participants reflect systemic challenges in rural education settings. However, these findings suggest these constraints may have particular significance in middle school mathematics, where the complexity of content and the importance of foundational skills for future academic success create additional pressures. The scheduling challenges and increased planning demands reported by participants indicate a need for innovative approaches to time management and resource allocation in rural middle schools.

Implications for Practice

The findings from this study suggest several important implications for educational practice, particularly in the context of rural middle school mathematics instruction. The high percentage of non-math-certified teachers leading intervention groups necessitates a comprehensive approach to professional development and support. Schools and districts must develop targeted training programs that address both mathematical content knowledge and pedagogical strategies specific to middle school intervention. These programs should extend beyond traditional workshop models to include ongoing mentorship and collaborative learning opportunities.

The success of small group instruction reported by participants suggests that schools should prioritize creating and maintaining these instructional arrangements, even in the face of staffing and scheduling challenges. This might

involve creative scheduling solutions and the development of flexible grouping strategies that maximize the use of available personnel while ensuring students receive appropriate support. The establishment of mentor relationships between math-certified and non-math-certified teachers could provide crucial support for those less comfortable with mathematical content while building institutional capacity for effective intervention.

The student engagement challenges revealed in this study indicate a need for middle school-specific intervention strategies that acknowledge the unique developmental needs of adolescent learners. Schools should consider developing intervention approaches that incorporate real-world applications and technology integration while maintaining rigorous mathematical content. The reported increase in student confidence suggests that intervention programs should explicitly address both academic skills and mathematical self-efficacy.

Study Limitations

Several important limitations must be considered when interpreting the results of this study. The reliance on self-reported data through questionnaires, while allowing for broad participation across multiple districts, limited the ability to directly observe classroom practices and student-teacher interactions. The absence of classroom observations means that the relationship between reported practices and actual implementation remains unexplored.

The geographic scope of the study, confined to rural Tennessee, potentially limits the generalizability of findings to other contexts. While many of the challenges identified likely resonate with rural schools across the country, specific state policies and regional characteristics may influence both the implementation of

RTI² and educators' perceptions of its effectiveness. The moderate sample size of 25 participants, though sufficient for qualitative insight, may not capture the full range of experiences in rural middle school math intervention.

Recommendations for Future Research

The findings of this study suggest several promising directions for future research in rural middle school mathematics intervention. A pressing need exists for investigation into effective professional development models for non-math-certified teachers who provide mathematics intervention. Such research should examine both content-focused training and pedagogical support, with particular attention to the unique challenges of rural school settings.

Longitudinal studies tracking student progress through middle school mathematics intervention programs would provide valuable insight into the long-term effectiveness of various intervention strategies. These studies should incorporate multiple measures of success, including not only academic achievement but also mathematical confidence and engagement. The positive findings regarding student confidence in this study suggest that affective factors deserve particular attention in future research.

Comparative studies examining implementation differences between rural and urban settings could illuminate how context-specific factors influence program effectiveness. Such research might identify successful strategies that could be adapted across settings while highlighting areas where rural schools require unique approaches. Additionally, investigation into successful scheduling and staffing models could provide practical guidance for schools struggling with resource allocation.

Research incorporating student and parent perspectives would provide a more complete picture of intervention effectiveness. While this study focused on educator perceptions, understanding how students experience mathematics intervention and how parents view its impact could inform program improvements. Such research might particularly examine the relationship between student engagement and intervention effectiveness, a concern highlighted by participants in this study.

Conclusion

This study contributes significant insights to the limited literature on math RTI² implementation in rural middle schools. The findings reveal both promising outcomes and substantial challenges that merit attention from educators, administrators, and policymakers. While improved academic performance and increased student confidence suggest the potential of well-implemented intervention programs, the prevalence of non-math-certified teachers leading intervention groups presents a critical challenge requiring immediate attention.

This investigation revealed three primary benefits of math RTI² implementation: improved academic performance on state assessments, increased student confidence and mathematical self-efficacy, and advantages of small-group instruction. Simultaneously, participants identified significant barriers, including staffing and qualification issues, time and resource constraints, and student engagement challenges. These findings illuminate the complex reality of implementing mathematical intervention programs in rural middle schools.

The results point to several essential elements for successful implementation: systematic professional development targeted to teachers' specific needs, strategic

scheduling and resource allocation that maximizes instructional effectiveness, and intervention approaches specifically designed for middle school students. The challenges identified, particularly regarding teacher qualifications and student engagement, suggest that rural schools require targeted support and resources to implement RTI² effectively.

These findings have significant implications for educational policy and practice, particularly regarding teacher preparation and professional development. The success of mathematics intervention in rural middle schools appears to depend heavily on building capacity among all teachers involved in intervention delivery, regardless of their original certification area. As schools continue to refine their intervention programs, attention to both the academic and affective components of mathematical learning will be crucial for supporting student success.

Future research should build on these findings by examining specific intervention strategies, professional development approaches, and implementation models that can address the unique challenges of rural middle school mathematics instruction. By continuing to investigate and address these challenges, educators can work toward ensuring that all students receive effective mathematical support, regardless of their geographic location or school resources.

References

- Bailey, T. R. (2014). An initial exploratory analysis of RTI implementation in rural schools. *The Researcher*, 26(1), 34–39.
- Berkeley, S., Scanlon, D., Bailey, T. R., Sutton, J. C., & Sacco, D. M. (2020). A snapshot of RTI implementation a decade later: New picture, same story. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 53(5), 332–342.
- Bouck, E. C., & Cosby, M. D. (2018). Response to Intervention in high school mathematics: One school's implementation. *Preventing School Failure: Alternative Education for Children and Youth*, 63(1), 32–42.
- Bouck, E. C., Park, J., Bouck, M. K., Alspaugh, J., & Spitzley, S. (2019). Exploration of a middle school Tier II math lab on student performance. *Preventing School Failure: Alternative Education for Children and Youth*, 63(1), 89–95.
- Bouck, E. C., Park, J., Bouck, M. K., Sprick, J., & Buckland, A. (2019). Implementing a RTI Tier II mathematics lab in a middle school. *Preventing School Failure: Alternative Education for Children and Youth*, 63(3), 269–276.
- Ciullo, S., Lembke, E. S., Carlisle, A., Thomas, C. N., Goodwin, M., & Judd, L. (2016). Implementation of evidence-based literacy practices in middle school Response to Intervention: An observation study. *Learning Disability Quarterly*, 39(1), 44–57.
- Dennis, M. S. (2015). Effects of Tier II and Tier III mathematics interventions for second graders with mathematics difficulties. *Learning Disabilities Research & Practice*, 30(1), 29–42.
- Deno, S. L., Reschly, A. L., Lembke, E. S., Magnusson, D., Callender, S. A., Windram, H., & Stachel, N. (2009). Developing a school-wide progress-monitoring system. *Psychology in the Schools*, 46(1), 44–55.
- Dobbins, A., Gagnon, J. C., & Ulrich, T. (2014). Teaching geometry to students with math difficulties using graduated and peer-mediated instruction in a Response-to-Intervention model. *Preventing School Failure: Alternative Education for Children and Youth*, 58(1), 17–25.
- Dulaney, S. K. (2012). A middle school's Response-to-Intervention journey. *National Association of School Principals Bulletin*, 97(1), 53–77.
- Faggella-Luby, M., & Wardwell, M. (2011). RTI in a middle school: Findings and practical implications of a Tier II reading comprehension study. *Learning Disability Quarterly*, 34(1), 35–49.

- Fuchs, D., & Fuchs, L. S. (2017). Critique of the National Evaluation of Response to Intervention: A case for simpler frameworks. *Exceptional Children*, 83(3), 255–268.
- Fuchs, L. S., & Fuchs, D. (2006). A framework for building capacity for responsiveness to intervention. *School Psychology Review*, 35(4), 621-626.
- Fuchs, L. S., Fuchs, D., & Compton, D. L. (2010). Rethinking Response to Intervention at middle and high school. *School Psychology Review*, 39(1), 22–28.
- Fuchs, L. S., Fuchs, D., Compton, D. L., Bryant, J. D., Hamlett, C. L., & Seethaler, P. M. (2007). Mathematics screening and progress monitoring at first grade: Implications for responsiveness to intervention. *Exceptional Children*, 73(3), 311–330.
- Individuals with Disabilities Education Improvement Act of 2004, Pub. L. No. 108–466. (2004).
- King, D. D. (2011). *Teacher understanding and perception of a Response to Intervention program in a rural, western North Carolina school district*. [Doctoral dissertation, Gardner Webb University]. Electronic Theses and Dissertations.
- No Child Left Behind Act of 2001, Pub. L. No. 107-110, 115 Stat. 1425. (2002).
- Prewett, S., Mellard, D. F., Deshler, D. D., Allen, J., Alexander, R., & Stern, A. (2012). Response to Intervention in middle schools: Practices and outcomes. *Learning Disabilities Research & Practice*, 27(3), 136–147.
- Robinson, G. G., Bursuck, W. D., & Sinclair, K. D. (2013). Implementing RTI in two rural elementary schools: Encouraging beginnings and challenges for the future. *The Rural Educator*, 34(3), 1–9.
- Sanger, D., Friedli, C., Brunken, C., Snow, P., & Ritzman, M. (2012). Educators' year long reactions to the implementation of a Response to Intervention (RTI) model. *Journal of Ethnographic & Qualitative Research*, 7(2), 9-107.
- Swanson, E., Solis, M., Ciullo, S., & McKenna, J. W. (2012). Special education teachers' perceptions and instructional practices in Response to Intervention implementation. *Learning Disability Quarterly*, 35(2), 115-126.
- Tennessee Department of Education. (2013). *Response to Instruction and Intervention framework*.